

MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF GRAPHITE-REINFORCED ALUMINUM METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Mechanical properties of two-ply unidirectionally reinforced P100/6061 graphite/aluminum metal matrix composite (MMC) were investigated. Standard tensile tests generated material properties data in longitudinal and long transverse orientations at room and cryogenic temperatures. Back-to-back strain gage triaxial rosettes enabled calculation of material ultimate and yield strengths, Young's modulus, ductility, and Poisson's ratio. Investigation of heat treatment response led to development of an optimized 6061-T6 heat treatment schedule tailored specifically to this MMC. Room- and cryogenic-temperature tensile properties demonstrated effects of this optimized treatment. Off-axis tensile properties, at 12-degree and 45-degree offset angles from the longitudinal material axis, were measured and compared to theoretical properties curves. Theoretical properties were determined from known parent material properties, accepted theories of composite mechanics, and the Tsai-Hill failure criterion. Computer code was prepared and curves were generated that compared favorably to test data. Shear properties, shear strengths, and modulus were developed from off-axis data and were also found to compare favorably to theory. Microstructural characteristics were metallographically documented. Thermal expansivity was measured in three axes, longitudinal, long transverse, and short transverse, by thermomechanical analysis.

KEYWORDS: Composite; Metal-Matrix; Testing; Mechanical Properties; Shear.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the mid-1980s, a joint U.S. Air Force/Navy program was initiated to establish producibility of and generate a design data base for graphite-reinforced aluminum metal matrix composite (MMC). The program, which came to be known as "Big Buy," pursued

this goal by providing manufacturers with 500 pounds of government-furnished 2,000-filament P100 yarn that was to be processed into a unidirectionally reinforced aluminum matrix composite. Purchase guarantees enabled manufacturers to sufficiently scale up and develop process parameters and quality control standards for composite production. With process reproducibility established, a production run of P100 reinforced 6061 aluminum alloy ensued. The resulting MMC was allocated to interested independent contractors, among them Rockwell's Space Systems Division, for test and evaluation.

Rockwell's participation in the Big Buy program resulted in the allocation of two sheets, 33 cm by 66 cm by 0.10 cm (13 inches by 26 inches by 0.040 inch), of two-ply unidirectional MMC. The composite construction consisted of two layers of metallized graphite wire sandwiched by two foils of 6061 aluminum. Nominal fiber volume fraction was 40 percent. Rockwell used its allocation of MMC to generate thermophysical properties, namely, coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE), and mechanical properties, including tensile and shear behavior and response to material heat-treatment aging. A heat-treatment cycle optimized for maximum positive material response was developed for the aging study.

2. STATEMENT OF PURPOSE

Each contractor participating in the test and evaluation portion of Big Buy was given wide latitude in the selection of specific properties investigations and test methodologies. Rockwell's approach was influenced by the relatively immature state of MMC technology. We chose to verify baseline material mechanical properties at cryogenic and room temperatures, determine response to precipitation heat treatment, measure variation of coefficient of thermal expansion with axis orientation, generate material shear properties data, and compare results to theoretical projections based on lamination theory.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.1 Tensile Test Tensile specimens and like-oriented grip tabs were diamond-abrasive-saw cut in orientations 0 degree, 12 degrees, 45 degrees, and 90 degrees, per Figure 1, from the two unidirectional panels as indicated in the specimen layout plans of Figures 2 and 3. Sixty-three specimens in all were machined, 43 of which were subjected to optimized T6 heat treatment prior to tab bonding and test. At least ten specimens in each orientation were prepared for T6 condition tensile test. All 63 specimens were instrumented with three-element back-to-back strain gage rosettes. Relative to the axis of each specimen, all but four had rosettes installed such that individual strain gage elements were oriented at 0 degree and +/-45 degrees. The remaining specimens, two at 0 degree and two at 90 degrees, had gage elements oriented at 0 degree, 45 degrees, and 90 degrees, to facilitate direct readout of longitudinal and transverse strains, largely as a check on the accuracy of rosette strain transformation calculations. Tensile tests were performed per standard laboratory procedures; testing was controlled and all data, load versus six channels of strain per specimen, were acquired with a Hewlett Packard 9845 computer system.

Notes:

1. Specimen and tabs to be cut at like orientations from the same panel of material.
2. Specimen thickness not to scale.

MTD 910226-1212

Figure 1. Tensile Specimen and Loading Grips

3.2 Coefficients of Thermal Expansion CTE specimens were diamond-abrasive-saw cut, at the same orientations as for tensile testing, as indicated in Figure 2. Specimens were prepared for pushrod dilatometry (1.27 cm by 7.62 cm [0.5 inch by 3.0 inches]) and for thermomechanical analysis (TMA) (0.64 cm by 0.64 cm [0.25 inch by 0.25 inch]). Dilatometry was used for CTE measurement in on- and off-axis orientations; through-the-thickness (short transverse) as well as on- and off-axis orientations were tested via TMA. Standard laboratory procedures were followed in all cases.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Tensile Tests Tensile test data were generated in the form of stress-strain curves as shown in Figure 4. Each of the six curves shown represents the output of load transducer versus output of one strain gage element (recall that each specimen had six elements). From each set of curves, rosette strain and stress transformation equations produced properties data, including Young's modulus, ultimate tensile strength, shear strength, shear modulus, Poisson's ratio, and strain to failure. Posttest failure analysis showed no evidence of colinearity of failure planes, and therefore, no apparent contribution of local material deficiencies to specimen failure. Room-temperature data are presented in Table 1; cryogenic (-150°C [-300°F]) data are shown in Table 2.

Referring to Tables 1 and 2, the following statements can be made:

- Data scatter was, in general, fairly tight and certainly within expectation for this type of material.

MATERIAL UTILIZATION (as cut) PLAN
Plate No. P100-6061-6061-G5786

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Figure 2. Cut Plan for Tensile and CTE Specimens, Plate P100-6061-6061-G5786

MATERIAL UTILIZATION (as cut) PLAN
Plate No. P100-6061-6061-G5777

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Figure 3. Cut Plan for Tensile Specimens, Plate P100-6061-6061-G5777

- Room-temperature data compare favorably with vendor certifications.
- Strains-to-failure varied significantly, behavior which was not surprising considering the material and the testing conducted.
- Poisson's ratio data were, in some cases, purposefully omitted because of irreconcilable data scatter.
- Ten specimens, all prepared in the very fragile 45-degree or 90-degree orientation, were lost (broken) during specimen preparation. Five additional specimens suffered instrumentation failures.

Figure 4. Typical Curves of Applied Stress Versus Strain Gage Output

Table 1. Room Temperature Tensile Properties

Orientation (degree)	Temperature	E (GPa)	F _{TU} (MPa)	G ₁₂ (GPa)	F _{SU} (MPa)	Poisson's Ratio	Strain to Failure (μ ϵ)	Failure Shear Strain (μ δ)
0 (longitudinal)	As received	357.1	734.3	—	—	—	—	—
12	As received	204.8	156.5	18.8	31.8	—	1004	1335
45	As received	48.4	43.5	19.9	21.7	0.22	1035	1327
90 (transverse)	As received	34.4	24.8	—	—	—	—	—
0 (longitudinal)	T6	354.4	672.9	—	—	0.34	1841	—
12	T6	202.7	183.4	18.1	37.4	0.32	1012	2521
45	T6	42.9	39.3	18.1	19.6	—	1004	1335
90 (transverse)	T6	31.0	22.1	—	—	0.04	753	—

Table 2. -150°C Tensile Properties

Orientation (degree)	Temperature	E (GPa)	F _{TU} (MPa)	G ₁₂ (GPa)	F _{SU} (MPa)	Poisson's Ratio	Strain to Failure (μ ϵ)	Failure Shear Strain (μ δ)
12	As received	200.6	211.0	18.0	42.9	0.26	1159	2944
45	As received	43.9	58.1	18.6	29.0	—	1212	—
0 (longitudinal)	T6	330.9	726.0	—	—	0.35	2137	—
12	T6	181.3	222.0	16.6	45.1	0.27	1267	3239
45	T6	46.8	56.1	16.6	28.1	—	1266	1783
90 (transverse)	T6	25.9	17.2	—	—	0.07	510	—

The tensile test data were used to corroborate existing theoretical models of composite strengths and stiffness.

Several theoretical models of composite material behavior were researched and integrated into a computer program to predict properties under off-axis tension loading. The curves following in this report were generated using primary (0 degree and 90 degrees) experimental material properties as input data.

The Tsai-Hill failure criterion provided analytical prediction of material ultimate strength based on fiber reinforcement angle theta. In its most useful form, for this purpose, Tsai-Hill can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\cos^4\Theta}{X^2} + \left(\frac{1}{S^2} - \frac{1}{X^2} \right) \cos^2\Theta \cdot \sin^2\Theta + \frac{\sin^4\Theta}{Y^2} = \frac{1}{\sigma_x^2} \quad (1)$$

where

X = composite longitudinal ultimate tensile strength

Y = composite transverse ultimate tensile strength

S = composite ultimate shear strength (L-T)

Θ = fiber reinforcement angle

σ_x = tensile strength at fiber angle theta

Figures 5 and 6 present curves generated from the Tsai-Hill equation coplotted with experimental tensile data from Tables 1 and 2. Theoretical predictions for off-axis orientations are well matched by experimental data.

Theoretical Young's modulus calculations were derived from tensor transformation of principal material compliances and an understanding of coupling of shear deformation with tensile loading in an off-axis unidirectional composite specimen. The predicted modulus curves of Figures 7 and 8 are a graphical representation of the equality:

$$\frac{1}{E_x} = \frac{\cos^4\Theta}{E_1} + \left(\frac{1}{G_{12}} - \frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_1} \right) \sin^2\Theta \cos^2\Theta + \frac{\sin^4\Theta}{E_2} \quad (2)$$

where

E_1 = composite longitudinal Young's modulus

E_2 = composite transverse Young's modulus

ν_{12} = composite Poisson's ratio

G_{12} = composite shear modulus

Θ = off-axis angle

Experimental data plotted with the curves again illustrate the close agreement of theory and experiment.

Generation of material shear properties was the prime driver of off-axis testing. Coupling of shear deformation and extensional loading, resulting from the unique construction of fiber-reinforced materials, occurs at off-axis angles in a predictable manner. Recognition of this behavior led to the evolution of off-axis testing as a simple, relatively inexpensive, and material-conservative method of determining shear strength and modulus, especially when compared to such methods as rail shear. Tsai-Hill has proved useful to describe shear strength as well as tensile strength. For tensile testing of off-axis specimens, failure shear strengths can be theoretically modelled by the following:

$$\frac{\cot^2\Theta}{X^2} + \frac{1}{S^2} - \frac{1}{X^2} + \frac{\tan^2\Theta}{Y^2} = \frac{1}{\tau_{12}^2} \quad (3)$$

where

τ_{12} = shear stress in L-T plane

It is important here to emphasize that ultimate shear strength differs from the shear stress level at specimen failure in an off-axis test. Pure shear is not developed; it exists in concert with a complex set of stresses generated by material characteristics and loading conditions. Any failure mode is attributable, therefore, to the combined effect of these stresses. Because pure shear is not developed, to use the term "ultimate shear strength" would be a misnomer for this application.

Tsai-Hill accounts for this combined stress state, and so, in Figures 7 and 8, the data, as well as the theoretical model, represent the maximum shear stress at failure, not ultimate shear strength per se. As illustrated by Figures 9 and 10, shear contribution to failure is maximized at off-axis angles in the neighborhood of 10 to 12 degrees. It is precisely for this reason that 12-degree specimens were chosen for test, the data generated therefrom being most closely in tune with pure shear behavior. Experimental data, as shown in Figures 9 and 10, while showing increased scatter, tend to compare favorably to theoretical prediction.

Shear modulus (G_{12}) for principal material directions can be theoretically derived similar to the derivation of Young's modulus. Young's modulus as a function of off-axis angle can be expressed as:

$$\frac{1}{E_x} = \frac{\cos^4\Theta}{E_1} + \left(\frac{1}{G_{12}} - \frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_1} \right) \sin^2\Theta \cdot \cos^2\Theta + \frac{\sin^4\Theta}{E_2} \quad (4)$$

Rearrangement of this equation yields predicted G_{12} based on known off-axis modulus. Since G_{12} is independent of off-axis orientation, any off-axis specimen will suffice for this prediction. Experimentally determined off-axis tensile moduli (as-received and heat-treated averages) were used for the following predictions of shear modulus. At 12-degree off-axis angle, room-temperature G_{12} was computed to be 17.4 GPa (2.53 msi); at 45 degrees, $G_{12} = 18.1$ GPa (2.63 msi). G_{12} at -300°F was predicted to be 16.4 GPa (2.38 msi) and 16.5 GPa (2.39 msi) for 12 degrees and 45 degrees, respectively. Experimental values for as-received material averaged 18.8 to 19.9 GPa (2.73 to 2.88 msi) at room temperature (12 degrees and 45 degrees, respectively) and 18.0 and 18.6 GPa (2.61 and 2.70 msi) for cryogenic tests (12 degrees and 45 degrees, respectively). Heat-treated material showed slightly lesser average values of 18.1 and 18.1 GPa (2.63 and 2.62 msi) at room temperature and 16.6 and 16.6 GPa (2.41 and 2.41 msi) at cryogenic temperature.

4.2 Heat Treat Response Tables 1 and 2 and Figures 5 through 10 indicate that optimized heat treat was found to create a small but discernible improvement in material properties. Ultimate strengths, as a group, are higher for heat-treated specimens when compared to the as-received, as are failure shear stresses. Young's modulus and shear modulus, again when evaluated as a group, are slightly reduced. The data confirm a limited positive effect of heat treatment on matrix-dominated properties.

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Figure 5. Predicted and Actual Off-Axis Ultimate Strengths at Room-Temperature

Figure 6. Predicted and Actual Off-Axis Ultimate Strengths at -300°F

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Figure 7. Predicted and Actual Off-Axis Young's Moduli at Room Temperature

MTD 910226-1218

Figure 8. Predicted and Actual Off-Axis Young's Moduli at -300°F

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Figure 9. Predicted and Actual Off-Axis Failure Shear Stresses at Room-Temperature

MTD 910226-1220

Figure 10. Predicted and Actual Off-Axis Failure Shear Stresses at -300°F

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4.3 Coefficients of Thermal Expansion Table 3 presents CTE data as generated by two methods, pushrod dilatometry and TMA. Expected fiber-reinforced composite behavior was observed here. Expansivity was lowest for the 0-degree orientation, showed slight increase at 12 degrees, jumped an order of magnitude from there to 45 degrees, doubled from 45 degrees to 78 degrees, and showed a slight increase from 78 degrees to 90 degrees. The 0-degree orientation showed expansivity closest to that of P100 fiber ($\alpha = 1.40$ millionths per °C [0.78 millionths per °F]). The 90-degree orientation exhibited behavior closest to that of pure 6061 alloy (where $\alpha = 23$ millionths per °C [13 millionths per °F]). Through-the-thickness (short transverse) specimens exhibited the highest expansivity and displayed strikingly nonlinear behavior above 40°C (100°F).

Table 3. Comparison of Coefficients of Thermal Expansion by Two Methods

Specimen Off-Axis Angle (Degrees)	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (millionths/°C)			
	Low Temperature (<RT)		High Temperature (>RT)	
	TMA	Dilatometer	TMA	Dilatometer
0	1.1	1.4	2.2	1.4
12	1.1	2.2	2.2	2.5
45	11.7	11.2	14.2	14.9
78	22.1	22.0	27.4	25.6
90 (T)	23.8	22.9	27.4	30.2
90 (ST)	25.4	—	*	—

*Highest expansivity observed here, but behavior was nonlinear, hence, CTE was not quoted.
Notes: Each datum is average of two.
< RT = mean CTE from -100°C to room temperature
> RT = mean CTE from room temperature to 200°C

5. REFERENCES

1. R. M. Jones, Mechanics of Composite Materials, Hemisphere Publishing Co., 1975.
2. F.P. Beer and E.R. Johnston, Jr., Mechanics of Materials, McGraw-Hill Publishers, 1981.
3. S.W. Tsai, Composites Design, 1987.
4. N.J. Pagano and J. C. Halpin, "Influence of End Constraint in the Testing of Anisotropic Bodies." Journal of Composite Materials, January 1968.

